

MANAGEMENT IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ZONING SYSTEM PPDB POLICY AS AN EFFORT TO EQUATE ACCESS AND QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN CIAMIS REGENCY (CASE STUDY AT SMAN 1 AND SMAN 2 CIAMIS)

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Abstract

This research is motivated by the pros and cons of the zoning system's New Student Admissions (PPDB) policy. Considering these problems and objectives, it is important to manage the implementation of the PPDB zoning system in educational units. Management steps according to Terry include planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating. These steps are taken in an effort to guide schools to achieve equal distribution of quality and access to educational services so that the output and outcomes obtained can be in accordance with the objectives of the issuance of the PPDB zoning system policy. The research results show that the implementation of the PPDB zoning system in Ciamis Regency has carried out all PPDB stages according to the guidelines, but has not been optimal in the implementation and supervision stages.

A. INTRODUCTION

This research is motivated by the pros and cons of the zoning system's New Student Admissions (PPDB) policy. Basically, the implementation of the zoning system in Indonesia was inspired by other countries that implemented it first. The zoning system is widely implemented because of its ability to objectively increase educational equality in these countries. Likewise in Indonesia, zoning is expected to be able to overcome gaps in access and quality of education in various regions (Ministry of Communication and Information Technology, 2019). Arguments for implementing a zoning system often refer to the phenomenon of success in developed countries (Wahyuni, 2018:15). However, what is often overlooked is that the conditions for implementing policies cannot be separated from other, broader policy contexts.

In fact, the zoning systems that develop in these countries do not work alone. Along with radical changes to student admission systems, these countries are also accelerating the increase in teacher capacity and the provision of facilities in educational institutions (Cheng, 2020: 86). The government also encourages competition between public and

private education so that schools continue to innovate in developing themselves (Lakes & Carter, 2011: 109). In Finland, for example, each school even has the freedom to experiment with learning methods and there is no strict standardization of values between all educational units (Poder, et.al. 2016: 352).

Basically, zoning is a development of rayonization. When rayonization is the division of areas based on agreement, zoning places more emphasis on dividing areas according to their function and management objectives. However, in its implementation, problems with the implementation of the zoning system cannot be denied, including the priority of the distance between prospective students' residence and school as the main determinant of PPDB which is difficult to implement, because the number of school graduates and the availability of schools for all regions is not yet balanced. As a result, several schools which initially had many students became limited and schools which initially had a shortage of prospective students became surplus prospective students because they were in dense zones (Wahyuni, 2018:15).

One of the negative impacts of the PPDB policy is described in the Study of the PPDB Zoning System, by the Education and Culture Policy Research Center (2017:58). The research results show that using a zoning system has triggered pros and cons in implementing the PPDB zoning system. Zoning mapping is considered unfair and uneven. The survey results in this research showed that there was disappointment from high-achieving students who could not enter their favorite schools. The implementation of the zoning policy is considered to be hasty without paying attention to the readiness of educational institutions and the community as policy targets.

Another problem is related to regulating the ratio of teachers and students due to the limited capacity of each state school, especially in the urban area of Ciamis. This is as per the research results of Cahyono (2019:23). Journal of Education, 1(1), shows that there are pros and cons related to the unequal distribution of quality teachers. In this research, it was stated that many quality teachers are concentrated in schools with the title of favorite school, so their presence needs to be spread through equal distribution of quality in each educational institution.

B. RESEARCH METHODE

This research uses a qualitative approach. A qualitative approach is expected to be able to produce in-depth descriptions of speech, writing or behavior that can be observed from certain individuals, groups, communities or organizations.

The method used is descriptive qualitative, namely empirical research in which data is collected and presented not in the form of numbers, but in narrative form. The data collected will be used as a basis for creating a description of the implementation of strategic management in improving the quality of education.

C. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Terry (1968) explains that "Management is a distinct process consisting of planning, organizing, actuating, and controlling, performed to determine and accomplish stated objectives by the use of human beings and other resources". Management is a unique process, which consists of actions: planning, organizing, mobilizing and monitoring, which are carried out to determine and achieve predetermined targets through the use of human resources and other sources.

Several efforts have been made to improve the quality and access to education services, one of which is the issuance of a policy for Admission of New Students with a zoning system. Zoning policy is an alternative chosen by the government in an effort to overcome educational problems that have been experienced by Indonesia, especially in terms of unequal distribution of quality and access to education services which are closely related to the economic and social fields. This is as Dunn (2003) states that "Public policy is a list of interconnected action options prepared by government agencies or officials, including in the fields of defense, education, welfare, crime control and urban development."

Considering these problems and objectives, it is important to manage the implementation of the PPDB zoning system in educational units. Management steps according to Terry (1968) include planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating. These steps are taken in an effort to guide schools to achieve equal distribution of quality and access to educational services so that the output and outcomes obtained can be in accordance with the objectives of the issuance of the PPDB zoning system policy. As Crosby (in Sallis, 2011: 70), states that "quality is in accordance with what is required or standardized (Conformance to requirements), namely in accordance with predetermined quality standards, both input, process and output."

1. Management planning for the implementation of the PPDB zoning system policy as an effort to equalize access and quality of education at SMAN 1 and SMAN 2 Ciamis Regency.

The government implements the zoning system with full consideration regarding planning, benefits and consequences. According to Syafitri (2019:10), as a basis for policy planning, the minister of education stated that every child of the nation has the same right to quality education services so that there is no discrimination, exclusivism and excessive competition to obtain government services. Public schools as public services must be able to create education with these ideal values (Locatelli, 2018).

To achieve these educational goals, agencies or schools must be able to access them (non-excludable), there is no intense competition (nonrivalry), and there is no discrimination (nondiscrimination) (Coughlan, 2018:349). Thus, achieving the goal of zoned schools is not only for equitable access to education services, but also for achieving optimal student academic achievement as a product of educational outcomes.

At the planning stage, Ciamis district public high school has prepared the structure of the school's online PPDB committee which consists of the person in charge, chairman,

secretary, treasurer, public relations and members. PPDB committee for departments and schools related to online PPDB. In its implementation, there is coordination carried out via the website between service operators and school operators when the process of accepting new students takes place on the e-System. The final stage in planning the PPDB zoning system is to prepare the PPDB Implementation Budget. Ciamis Regency State High School, in this case, has used School Operational Assistance (BOS) funds.

The things that are planned for the online-based admission of new students are attached in accordance with the technical instructions and implementation instructions for the implementation guidelines for the admission of new students for the 2021/2022 academic year based on the decision of the West Java Provincial Education Office.

The PPDB planning for the zoning system at State High School level in Ciamis district has been designed based on the technical manual and implementation guidelines for Admission of New Students for 2021/2022. The planning stage includes; 1) determine PPDB policy standards and 2) formulate activities or work plans that will be implemented to achieve successful PPDB implementation as determined in an SOP (Standard Operational Procedure), 3) prepare a PPDB implementation schedule, 4) prepare a Budget.

Zoning-based PPDB planning carried out by Ciamis State High School also designs PPDB based on applicable government regulations (Wardhana & Supriyoko, 2019:44). Based on this opinion, the determination of the objectives of the PPDB zoning system at the State High School level in Ciamis district has been guided by the technical manual and implementation guidelines for Admission of New Students in 2021 as follows; Objectivity, meaning that the acceptance of students must meet the requirements. Transparency, meaning that the implementation of student admissions is open and can be known to the public, including students' parents, to avoid possible irregularities. Accountability, meaning that the acceptance of students can be accounted for to the community both regarding procedures and results. Non-discriminatory, meaning that every citizen of school age can take part in educational programs in the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia without distinguishing between region of origin, religion and class. Determination of requirements for new students based on a joint decree from the Head of the Education Service.

Allocation of School Operational Assistance funds in promotion and outreach planning is legal and reasonable, and in budgeting planning determines the success of implementing activities (Wardhana & Supriyoko, 2019:45). This opinion is similar to findings in the field that the final stage in planning the PPDB zoning system is to prepare the PPDB Implementation Budget, Ciamis Regency State High School in this case has used School Operational Assistance funds.

2. Organizing the management of implementing the PPDB zoning system policy as an effort to equalize access and quality of education at SMAN 1 and SMAN 2 Ciamis Regency.

Organizing is the activity of following up on planning with the assistance of all members of the organization within it and providing development and services to those who support it. In the organizing function, activities are determined, dividing work and more specific tasks, and determining who has the authority to complete certain tasks (Arif, 2020; Hanifah, 2018). Organizing involves several activities, namely determining members, determining the organizational structure, and delegate tasks. Empowering teachers and school staff as PPDB committees is a form of human resource management.

Based on these opinions, it can be concluded that the organization of the PPDB zoning system in State High Schools has been carried out, but is not optimal due to the uneven distribution of the IT capabilities of the PPDB Team. The organizing stage begins with forming a PPDB Team and dividing tasks or job descriptions by the Principal as the person responsible for PPDB.

3. Implementation of management of the implementation of the PPDB zoning system policy as an effort to equalize access and quality of education at SMAN 1 and SMAN 2 Ciamis Regency.

The implementation of zoning-based PPDB at State High Schools in Ciamis Regency follows Regency Government regulations. The provisions of the zoning system are stated in the 2021 Ciamis Regency PPDB Technical Guidelines regarding technical instructions for accepting new students in Kindergartens, Elementary Schools and Junior High Schools in 2021-2022.

The principal of the State High School revealed that the school followed the rules of the government's technical guidelines during the zoning-based PPDB. Starting from the registration process, to the re-registration process, both schools carry out it according to the rules stated above. If we analyze in depth the zoning-based PPDB that uses this online system, it projects two characteristics of work from the two schools, namely passive and active work.

The implementation of PPDB by all PPDB committees is said to be truly passive if what is meant is the internal committee or the committee that works within the school. However, it can be said to be active for external committees or committees that have the task of assisting PPDB operations at the Ciamis Regency Service, because during the registration process the person who is active is the admin from the Department. On the other hand, the internal committee can be said to be active, namely when carrying out offline registration services. Having offline services is a step taken by both schools to overcome the presence of parents who do not understand the online PPDB registration process even though it has actually been recommended in the technical guidelines above. This is made clear by the finding that both schools provide a special place for PPDB guest services.

This fact is in line with research at SMA Sultan Trenggono Gunungpati Semarang that the registration mechanism at the school is offline and online without selection, but in reality more prospective students register offline (Nurlailiyah, 2019:14). The existence of offline services intended to help parents register their children is a negative impact of the PPDB with an online system.

Based on the findings, at the beginning of the year the zoning-based PPDB was implemented, both schools felt they did not get as many student quotas as last year before the zoning-based PPDB policy was implemented. So it can be interpreted that last year's zoning-based PPDB was said to be ineffective and inefficient. Apart from that, the response from both schools was also low regarding the existence of zoning-based PPDB in the first year. However, slowly the two schools adapted and improved the existing implementation with various preparations. This year, State High Schools made various preparations, such as carrying out promotions through nearby junior high schools. Apart from that, State High Schools also carry out a number of promotions starting from promotions to nearby junior high schools, promotions via print media, promotions via social media (social media), to promotions via radio.

Based on this data, it can be seen that there has been an increase in the average exam score at State High School level in the last three years, namely in 2020/2021 it reached 87.50%, in 2021/2022 it reached 87.68% and in 2021/2022 it reached 91.80% . From the increase in the average score of the State High School National Examination in Kab. Ciamis can be concluded that the implementation of the PPDB zoning system policy has succeeded in increasing student achievement.

Based on these opinions, it can be concluded that the implementation of PPDB Zoning in SMA Negeri Kab. Ciamis has implemented the acceptance of new students based on a zoning system, even though it has pros and cons, the District. Ciamis has been successful in increasing equitable access and quality of education.

4. Management supervision of the implementation of the PPDB zoning system policy as an effort to equalize access and quality of education at SMAN 1 and SMAN 2 Ciamis Regency.

Supervision is a very important activity so that the work and tasks assigned to implementing officials are carried out in accordance with established plans (Berlian, 2011: 81). This is in accordance with the opinion of Syafarah and Wibowo (2018:104). which states that supervision is a process of observing the implementation of all organizational activities to ensure that all work being carried out runs according to a predetermined plan. According to Koonz, et al, quoted by (Fadillah, 2020:39) said that supervision is measuring and correcting the activities of subordinates to ensure that what is carried out is in accordance with the plan. So supervision measures implementation compared to ideals and plans, shows where there are negative deviations and by mobilizing actions to correct deviations, helps ensure the achievement of plans. The concept of supervision actually shows that supervision is part of the management function, in where supervision is considered as a form of inspection or control from a higher party to a lower party."

The PPDB supervision pattern is zoning-based, supervision activities are carried out by the school principal as the person responsible for the PPDB. The school principal holds an evaluation meeting at the end of every PPDB service hour. This meeting is held during the registration process for new students. The evaluation meeting was held with the aim of finding out and providing an assessment of the process of implementing the registration of new students, whether it was running in accordance with the technical instructions, whether there were any deficiencies or errors. If there is, it can be detected and repaired as soon as possible. So that the registration process for new students in the future and the next academic year can run better. The school principal also holds a meeting before making the PPDB journal or report. In this meeting you can also ask for opinions or input for further PPDB evaluations, you can also hear about the obstacles faced by the PPDB committee. Apart from that, another form of supervision is monitoring or evaluation carried out by the Ciamis Regency Education Office. The Department carries out monitoring during the PPDB implementation process as a form of preparedness if problems or obstacles occur. Meanwhile, the evaluation is carried out after the PPDB ends by looking at the final report prepared by the school. Monitoring carried out by the Department uses on desk techniques and on site techniques.

The on desk technique is the implementation of monitoring carried out by observing progress reports, and the on site technique is by carrying out monitoring directly in the field. These two techniques are combined with the aim of avoiding deviations or errors so that they can be corrected and ensure that policy implementation moves towards the desired goals. Thus, it can be concluded that supervision activities are carried out by the school principal as the person responsible for the PPDB. The online PPDB process at high school level in Kab. Ciamis has gone through a monitoring process both on desk and on site, namely during the implementation, monitoring/supervision is carried out by the Ciamis Regency Education Office, to be precise during the written test process up to the final calculation which is broadcast online via social media.

5. Management Barriers to Implementing the PPDB Zoning System Policy as an Effort to Equalize Access and Quality of Education at SMAN 1 and SMAN 2, Ciamis Regency, West Java.

In the educational context, policy implementation is an effort or effort so that educational policy formulations can be implemented in practice, because no matter how good the educational policy formulation is, if it is not implemented, the benefits will not be felt by the community. On the other hand, no matter how simple the educational policy formulation is, if it has been implemented, it will be worse. whatever use it may have and whatever the results. (Arwildayanto, 2018:78)

Field facts show that public high schools face various obstacles and challenges, both internal and external.

The following are some of the internal obstacles faced in implementing the PPDB zoning system at Ciamis State High School;

- a. School Capacity is Limited. Public High Schools find it difficult to accommodate all prospective students who live in certain zones, this results in the rejection of registration for prospective students who actually meet the zoning criteria.
- b. Supervision and Transparency. It is difficult for public high schools to ensure effective supervision and transparency in the zoning process is a challenge. A strong system is needed to prevent intervention or fraud.
- c. Lack of IT Resources. Public High Schools lack IT personnel so the PPDB process is less efficient. Implementation of a zoning system requires the support of adequate information technology resources.

Of these obstacles, the reason for the lack of IT resources can be a factor that greatly influences the New Student Admissions (PPDB) process for the zoning system in State High Schools. Lack of IT resources can cause various problems that affect efficiency, fairness and transparency in PPDB implementation.

6. Management Impact of Implementing the PPDB Zoning System Policy as an Effort to Equalize Access and Quality of Education at SMAN 1 and SMAN 2, Ciamis Regency, West Java.

The implementation of the zoning system in PPDB will have implications for the fading of the status of "leading schools" or "favorite schools" which will cause the existence of "castes" in the school system in Indonesia. This has the consequence that the government must prepare a system for managing and administering learning services that is of equal quality based on the quality standards set out in the National Education Standards (SNP).

Based on the triangulation results, there are two impacts from implementing the PPDB zoning system. First, the impact for parties who are pro the implementation of the zoning system is to get an objective usefulness value from the program, namely equal distribution of the quality of access to education. Increasing equal access to education can be seen from eliminating the stigma of favorite and non-favorite schools, reducing the distance students travel from home to school, and distributing students from various backgrounds and learning outcomes more evenly.

Second, the impact on opposing parties. Those who are against it see more weaknesses in the zoning system in terms of less than optimal technical implementation readiness. The technical weakness of implementing the zoning system causes side effects such as great disappointment because the desire to enter a school that is considered a favorite cannot be achieved because it comes from outside the zone. Schools which were originally the main goal for children to choose a school because of their favorite label are currently decreasing in interest, in some schools the quota for applicants is not even met considering the number of students in the zone is small, or conversely the number of school quotas is limited so not all students are in that zone accepted.

Basically, both pros and cons have their own reasons based on their personal point of view so they have different perspectives. Whatever the perception that society currently has, the real condition that must be faced is to follow the regulations and policies that have been set by the government for both those who are pro and con, regardless of their attitude towards these policies. However, the government's biggest homework is to prepare facilities to support an equitable zoning system. As stated by Ula, et al (2019:34). that "in the long term PPDB will be adaptive and implementable if the government maximizes school facilities and infrastructure"

Thus, it can be concluded that there are two impacts from implementing the PPDB zoning system. Firstly, the impact for parties who are pro for the implementation of the zoning system, namely those who get an objective benefit value from the zoning system and secondly, the impact for parties who are against it, namely those who feel disadvantaged, so they see more weaknesses in the zoning system from less than optimal implementation readiness.

D. CONCLUSION

The research results show that the implementation of the PPDB zoning system in Ciamis Regency has carried out all PPDB stages according to the guidelines, but has not been optimal in the implementation and supervision stages. There are two impacts from implementing the PPDB zoning system. Firstly, the impact for parties who are pro for the implementation of the zoning system, namely those who get an objective benefit value from the zoning system and secondly, the impact for parties who are against it, namely those who feel disadvantaged, so they see more weaknesses in the zoning system from less than optimal implementation readiness.

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